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The vision of the journals is to provide an academic platform to scholars all over the world to publish their novel, original, empirical and high quality research work. It propose to encourage research relating to latest trends and practices in international business, finance, banking, service marketing, human resource management, corporate governance, social responsibility and emerging paradigms in allied areas of management. It intends to reach the researcher's with plethora of knowledge to generate a pool of research content and propose problem solving models to address the current and emerging issues at the national and international level. Further, it aims to share and disseminate the empirical research findings with academia, industry, policy makers, and consultants with an approach to incorporate the research recommendations for the benefit of one and all.

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“GOVERNMENT INITIATIVES AND ISSUES INVOLVED IN WOMEN EMPOWERMENT”

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ABSTRACT

Even though women constitute 50 percent of the total population, we talk about women empowerment and not men empowerment. Need for women empowerment arose due to lots of reasons for example, centuries of exploitation and discrimination done by men over women and women are the suppressed lot. They are always the target group of different types of violence and discriminatory practices done by men not in India but all over the world. There are various reasons for such discriminatory behaviour against women such as male superiority complex and patriarchal system in society. There are various constitutional and legal rights available to eliminate and eradicate these ill practices but in reality there are a lot to be done in this regard. Many self-help groups (SHGs) and NGOs are working towards this end and also even women are breaking the societal barriers and achieving great heights in all spheres of life whether it may be political or social or economic. Even after so many measures taken the society is not still ready to accept women as being equal to men. Therefore, crimes or abuses against women are still on the rise. To change all these things the age-old deep-rooted mind set of the society needs to be changed through social re-engineering and gender sensitization programmes. In this regard, in 2017, University Grants Commission-Human Resource Development Centres have carried out short-term courses of one week on gender sensitization in all Indian universities where these centres are established. The present paper tries to find out the issues involved in women empowerment and analysed the government initiatives towards women empowerment. The paper ends with the conclusion that men and women both have to work to remove gender disparity and have to come on a common platform to work on gender sensitization.

KEYWORDS: *Women Empowerment, Gender Sensitization, Discrimination, Decision Making, Equal Rights.*

INTRODUCTION

Women empowerment may be referred as a creation of an environment especially for women where independent decisions can be taken by them for their own benefit as well as for the benefit for their family or for the society. The major benefit of women empowerment is that there will be an overall development of the society at large. Though women population constitutes approximately 50 percent of the world population but the reality is that a large number of women around the world are unemployed. As there is unequal opportunity for women at workplaces, the economy of the world suffers a lot. As uneducated women have a greater risk for domestic violence than an educated women, women empowerment leads to decrease in domestic violence.

In the words of Swami Vivekananda, “There is no chance for the welfare of the world unless the condition of women is improved; it is not possible for a bird to fly on only one wing.”

Women empowerment is all about:-

- Getting safe and cosy environment for work
- Participation in social, religious and other public activities with equal rights
- Freedom to make their own choices and decisions
- Equal rights for social and economic justice
- A feeling of self respect, worth and dignity

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

According to the World Bank’s 2012 World Development Report: Gender Equality and Development, closing these gender gaps matters for development and policymaking. Greater gender equality can enhance economic productivity, improve development outcomes for the next generation, and make institutions and policies more representative. According to Government of India report of 2009, “Participation of women in employment and decision-making remains far less than that of men, and the disparity is not likely to be eliminated by 2015. In addition, the labour market openness to women in industry and services has only marginally increased from 13-18 percent between 1990-1991 and 2004-2005.” The former secretary-general of the United Nations, Kofi Annan once stated, “There is no tool for development more effective than the empowerment of women.” As economic, political, and social actors, empowering women can change policy choices and make institutions more representative of a range of voices. In India, giving power to women at the local level led to greater provision of public goods, such as water and sanitation, which mattered more to women (Beaman et.al. 2011). Elimination of barriers against women working in certain sectors or occupations could increase output by raising women’s participation and labour productivity by as much as 25 percent in some countries through better allocation of their skills and talent (Cuberes and Teignier-Baqué, 2011).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is based on secondary data. The paper takes the references of various articles written by various experts on women empowerment and gender disparity. Also, opinion of various learned persons, women entrepreneurs and female social workers in Moradabad district of Uttar Pradesh respectively has been taken about the gender disparity, women empowerment, etc. Their views have been incorporated in this paper

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present paper aims at the following objectives:

- To characterise women empowerment;
- To find out the issues relating to women empowerment;
- To find out the initiatives taken up by Government of India for enhancing women empowerment;
- To present suggestions for empowering women in India

CHARACTERISTICS OF WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

Women empowerment can be characterised in the following points:

1. Women empowerment is all about giving power to women to be better off. It develops:
 - A sense of independence
 - An advanced degree of self-confidence among women.
2. Women empowerment is a process of acquiring power for women in order to:
 - Understand their rights
 - Perform their responsibilities towards oneself and others in a most effective way.
3. Women empowerment enables women to:
 - Organize themselves
 - Increase their self-reliance
 - Provides greater autonomy to them.
4. Women empowerment leads to:
 - Control over ideology and resources – material and intellectual.
 - Challenge traditional power equations and relations.
 - Exposing the harsh powers of prevalent gender social relations
5. Women empowerment enables:
 - The abolishment of any sort of discrimination based on gender in all spheres and structures of society
 - Ensures participation of women in decision-making process as well as policy framework at both domestic and public levels.
6. Women empowerment makes women more powerful to:
 - Face the challenges of life
 - Overcome to the disabilities , handicaps, and inequalities
 - Realize their full identity and powers in all spheres of life
7. Women empowerment also means:
 - Equal status to women

- Greater access to knowledge and resources
 - Greater autonomy in decision making
 - Greater ability to plan
 - Freedom from the restraints imposed on them by custom belief and practice.
8. Women empowerment occurs within:
- Political
 - Sociology
 - Cultural
 - Psychological
 - Ancestral
 - Economic Spheres
 - At various levels such as Individual, Group and Community.
9. Women empowerment is a process of:
- Creating awareness
 - Capacity building
10. Whenever there is a discrimination imposed by the male dominated society, women empowerment gives the power to resist it.

ISSUES RELATING TO WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

There are lots of issues which need to be addressed at various levels. The issues are mentioned herein below:-

(A) Issues relating to education:

- Lower levels of female education in India
- Considerable gender gaps in education
- Poor enrolment rates because of lack of household resources, huge workload at home, high school fees and lack of adequate facilities

(B) Issues relating to economy:

- Self-confidence is generally low which restraint the women to be economically prosperous
- Women act as an unpaid family workers in agriculture farms
- Long hours of working, women carrying the extra burden of household work in the family and farm
- Women's contribution to income and economic well-being of the family is not recognized
- Lots of barriers such as Social and cultural barriers which puts an exclusive responsibility on women for household work and restrictions on mobility, and so on and so forth.

(C) Issues relating to health:

- Lack of access to adequate health services, particularly reproductive health care and contraceptive devices.
- Families generally prefer male offspring.
- Maternal mortality rate is high
- High infant and child mortality rates and neglect of girls' health
- High male to female sex ratio.

CHALLENGES FOR WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

Women empowerment faces lot of challenges in our society. The important ones are:

1) Biased Perspective: It includes:

- Discrimination against the girl child
- Female infanticide is a common practice in our country.

2) Patriarchate Bottlenecks: It relates to:

- **Indian society is patriarchal.**
- **Women have no say in any decision of the family whether financial or otherwise**
- **Honour killing is one example of male dominated society**

3) Economic Backwardness:

- Indians fail in converting the available women power into human resource.
- No economic opportunities available to women
- Hampers economic development

4) Implementation Gaps: It includes gaps between developing and monitoring the schemes.

- Attention on devising various schemes for women
- No attention on implementation of the welfare schemes
- No monitoring of the welfare schemes

5) Loopholes in the legal structure:

- Legal system not effective in reducing crimes against women
- Delay in getting legal remedy and the presence of various loopholes in the functioning of a judicial system.

6) Lack of Political Will:

- Women's Reservation Bill still pending
- The dominance of male in Indian politics
- Women are forced to remain mute spectators.

GOVERNMENT INITIATIVES FOR WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

We can't say that government had done nothing towards women empowerment. There are lots of initiatives taken up by the government for the development of women. The important ones are highlighted below:-

- Article 14: Guarantees to all Indian women equality before law
- Article 39: The citizen, men & women equally have the right to an adequate means of livelihood.
- Article 39(d): Prevents the economic rights of women by guaranteeing equal pay for equal work
- Article 42: Securing just and humane condition of work and maternity relief for women
- Article 44: Uniform civil code for the citizens throughout the territory of India to safeguard women from laws of religion
- Article 51 A (e): One of the duties of every citizen is to renounce practices derogatory to the dignity of woman
- Panchayati Raj Institutions: All local elected bodies have reservation of 1/3 of their seats for women just to boost the position of women in politics. (73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendment Act)
- Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961: The Act prohibits payment or acceptance or request of a dowry. There is a punishment for it by way of imprisonment.
- Rastriya Mahila Kosh: To provide micro loans for women.
- Development of women & children in Rural Areas (DWCRA): Creation of groups of women for income generating activities on self sustaining basis.
- SABLA: Empowering adolescent girls.
- Sexual Harassment of Women at Work Place) Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013: The Act prohibits any type of sexual harassment at workplace. The Act creates a conducive and safe environment at the places where the women works.
- National Commission for Women: National commission for women is a statutory body that seeks to monitor and look matters related to legal and constitutional safeguards provided to women. It also review existing legislations and suggest amendments.
- *Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao Yojana*: Initiatives such as “*Beti Bacho, Beti Padhao Yojana*” (Save girl child, educate girl child) focus toward generating awareness and improving welfare services meant for women in India.
- Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005: The Act prevents the women from domestic violence. The Act protects the rights of women who are victims of domestic violence. A breach of Act attracts the punishment with fine or imprisonment or both.
- National Rural Health Mission: Creating awareness among women on health care. This resulted in the decline in fertility rates, Maternal Mortality Rates, Infant Mortality Rates.
- Self Help Groups: The banks give financial help to women self help groups for starting their business in groups. Regional Rural banks gave more emphasis on this. These SHGs act as a catalyst for women empowerment where women become independent in terms of earnings.
- Scheme for working women hostel: To promote availability of safe & conveniently located accommodation for working women.
- National Plan of Action for the Girl Child: The National Plan of Action for the girl child was made to ensure the protection, survival and development of girls.
- Women’s Reservation Bill: The bill is pending in India which allows the women a reservation of 33 percent of all seats in the Lok Sabha and in all Legislative Assemblies of the States. If passed, this Bill will give a thrust to women in Indian politics at the state and centre level.

ANALYSIS/FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The analysis/findings of the present study are highlighted below:

- 1) The gross enrolment ratio of female child is very low as compared to male child which suggests the lower level of female education in India.
- 2) During the discussion with women entrepreneurs, the fact came out is that women lack the self-confidence. Due to social system women are not allowed to go outside which hinders the path of success. It was also revealed that male members do not support their female family members in becoming self-reliant.
- 3) The discussion also shows the lack of access to adequate health services, particularly reproductive health care and contraceptive devices. Maternal mortality rate is high in India.
- 4) We find lots of challenges faced by women such as economic backwardness, patriarch society, implementation gap, loopholes in legal system, etc.
- 5) Various provisions/articles of the Indian Constitution guarantees to all Indian women equality before law.
- 6) Various Acts were enacted to protect the rights of the women such as Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961, Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005, Women's Reservation Bill, etc.
- 7) Rastriya Mahila Kosh, SABLA, *Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao Yojana*, SHGs, DWCRA, Janani Suraksha Yojana, etc are the various schemes launched by the Indian Government to raise the standard of life of the women.

SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

When we think of equal rights, a change is required in the perceptions of men and women to reduce gender disparity. The following suggestions are noteworthy in this regard:-

- Lot of gender disparities remain even as countries develop, which calls for sustained and firm public action. Corrective policies on the part of the government will definitely yield substantial development. To be successful and effective, these measures must focus at the root causes of inequality without ignoring the domestic political economy.
- In the process of empowerment women should do their SWOT analysis whereby consider their strengths, weakness, opportunities and threats and move ahead to unfold their own potential to achieve their goals through self-development. Nobody can empower women except women herself.
- Overall productivity of women can be increased if their skills and talents are used more efficiently and effectively. Potential of women is needed to be identified.
- Women empowerment is a two way process. Both men and women have to work on it. Women have to identify their potentials while men have to give respect to women and accepting them as equals. In this way a lot of inequalities relating to gender-based will reduce significantly.
- In order to bring gender equality, the government and other policymakers need to focus their attention on many priorities such as:-
 - a) Attempting to reduce the excess mortality of girls and women;
 - b) Try to eliminate the gender disadvantages in education;
 - c) Ensuring an increase in women's access to economic opportunity and thereby earnings as well as productivity;
 - d) Giving women an equal voice in households and other outside matters;
 - e) Across generations trying to limit the transmission of gender inequality

- A deep rooted patriarchate society with strong socio-cultural values continues to affect women empowerment. There is a need of an equal society, where there is no place for superiority and every men or women be treated equally.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study is not free from limitations. The few limitations are:

- The paper is conceptual in nature.
- The study is based on secondary data. However, researchers have discussed the matter of women empowerment with learned persons.
- Primary data on real examples of women empowerment has not been taken.
- The study does not reveal as to what extent government initiatives towards women empowerment have been successful.

CONCLUSION

To conclude we can say that women empowerment is an ongoing dynamic process that enhances women's abilities to change the structure and ideologies that keep them subordinate. Indian women though face lots of hurdles, problems and challenges it has not deterred their confidence and enthusiasm to bring about a powerful social change. They are moving on a new road which will lead them towards attaining empowerment both social and economic. To bring about gender equality, policymakers need to stress on important priorities such as eliminating gender gaps in education; reducing the high mortality rate; providing economic opportunity to women and thereby enhancing their earnings and productivity; giving an opportunity to women to have an equal voice in households and nearby areas; and last but not the least restraining the spread of gender inequality across the generations.

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Dear

DR. JEET SINGH

I am very pleased to inform you that your article/research paper titled **“GOVERNMENT INITIATIVES AND ISSUES INVOLVED IN WOMEN EMPOWERMENT”** has been published in **Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR)** (UGC approved journal No. 47638) (ISSN: 2278-4853) (Impact Factor: SJIF 2017 = 5.443) Vol.7, Issue- 10, October, 2018.

The scholarly paper provided invaluable insights on the topic. It gives me immense pleasure in conveying to your good self that our Editorial Board has highly appreciated your esteemed piece of work.

We look forward to receive your other articles/research works for publication in the ensuing issues of our journal and hope to make our association everlasting.

Thanking you once again

With Best Regards

Dr. Esha Jain
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3. At this stage, two referees will carefully review the research article, each of whom will make a recommendation to publish the article in its present form/modify/reject.
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